

Sustainable Management of Versioned Data

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Abstract—Efficient management of versioned (temporal) data is an important problem for a variety of business applications that require traceability of changes, auditing, or history analysis. However, practical concerns regarding scalability and sustainability that arise when running a versioned system for extended periods of time often remain unaddressed. In this paper, we present our approach for solving these issues in our implementation prototype¹. We state the requirements, provide an overview over the algorithm and a comparison with related work alongside a discussion of individual advantages, disadvantages and challenges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Working with versioned data, sometimes also referred to as *temporal* data, is an old problem. Early work dates back to 1986 when Richard Snodgrass presented his article *Temporal Databases* [1]. Since then, several authors have proposed various approaches [2][3][4] to efficiently solve the problem. In 2011, temporal features were introduced officially in the SQL Standard [5] which emphasizes the demand for such technology in practice. In 2016, we published a paper [6] that presents a novel approach to versioning using a matrix-based formalization, which will be summarized in Section II. This approach improved on the state of the art by offering equivalent “point-in-time” query performance on all versions, a compact format that maximizes sharing of unchanged data among versions and formalized operation semantics. Even though all of the mentioned publications offer solutions for the management of temporal data, there is one key aspect that has not yet been covered yet, which is the problem of building a system for temporal data management that can not only provide acceptable performance in short-term laboratory conditions, but can actually run for several years in a deployment, and is capable of dealing with the large volume of data accumulated over time via versioning. This issue is essential and even more prevalent than in non-versioned systems, because a deletion that would usually reduce the data volume actually results in a new version being created, increasing the number of managed elements instead. A similar line of argumentation holds for modifications. This sustainability problem is the main focus of this paper. We propose a new management technique for temporal data that expands upon our previous work and discuss its implications to implementation complexity and performance.

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The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Section II we provide an overview of our past work and related concepts. Section III introduces the problem of sustainable management for versioning data and presents the individual requirements in detail. In Section IV we outline our proposed solution and elaborate on its implications. After comparing our approach with related work in Section V, we provide an outlook to our future work in Section VI and conclude the paper with a summary in Section VII.

II. TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

In his paper *Efficient indexing for constraint and temporal databases* [2] from 1997, Sidhar Ramaswamy stated that the data versioning problem “is a generalization of two dimensional search which is known to be hard to solve”. In our experience, the complexity of the problem further increases with the expressivity of the chosen data model. For that reason, we decided to choose a simple basic format and then transform more sophisticated structures into that format. The basic format of choice here is a Key-Value Store that is enhanced with temporal information. This is the foundation for our *ChronoDB*² project [6]. This Temporal Key-Value Store operates on triples

$$\text{Entry} := \langle t, k, v \rangle$$

... where t is a Unix-style 64bit timestamp, k is an arbitrary string that acts as the key, and v is the value associated with the key, which is a byte array of arbitrary length greater zero. In contrast to other formalizations (e.g. [2]) our approach does not involve *validity ranges* in terms of lower and upper timestamp bounds. Instead, in our case the validity range is *implicit* – any given entry is valid until a new entry with the same key is inserted that has a higher timestamp, “overriding” the previous entry. This can be visualized as a matrix, as shown in Figure 1.

This figure shows the process of retrieving the value for key d at timestamp 5. The algorithm first tries to find the entry at the exact location, and then back-tracks and checks older timestamps. The first value encountered during this search is returned. This works because an entry that did not change from one timestamp to the next is assumed to have remained unchanged. Since entries, once written into the database, are

²Available on GitHub: <https://github.com/MartinHaeusler/chronos/tree/master/org.chronos.chronodb>

Fig. 1. Performing a *get* operation on a Temporal Data Matrix.

assumed to be immutable, copying their data is not necessary, thus maximizing sharing of unchanged data between versions. Furthermore, the fact that upper bounds of validity ranges are implicit in this structure, data that was once written to disk never needs to be modified again, allowing the implementation to be a true *append only* store. A modification or insertion both result in the execution of a *put* operation that inserts new entries. To ensure consistency of the history, new entries may only be added *after* the last entry on the time dimension, i.e. modification of the past is prohibited.

TABLE I
ASCENDING TEMPORAL KEY ORDERING BY EXAMPLE

Order	Temporal Key	User Key	Timestamp
0	a@0123	a	123
1	a@0124	a	124
2	a@1000	a	1000
3	aa@0100	aa	100
4	b@0001	b	1
5	ba@0001	ba	1

On the implementation side, our prototype ChronoDB relies on a B⁺-Tree structure [7] for its primary index, which is a regular B-Tree where the leaf nodes in addition form a linked list for fast neighbor search. In this index, the key (which we refer to as *temporal key*) is a string consisting of the original user key, a separator, and the timestamp of insertion (left-padded with zeros to give equal length to all timestamps). The tree is ordered by lexicographic ordering on the key, resulting in the order displayed in Table I. This ordering is critical for the implementation, because executing a temporal *get* operation as depicted in Figure 1 is now equivalent to finding the temporal key where the user key is identical to the given one, and the timestamp is either equal to or the *next-lower* contained timestamp compared to the request timestamp. The B⁺-Tree structure allows to perform this query efficiently with time complexity $O(\log n)$.

III. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION & REQUIREMENTS

In practice, a versioned data store may be deployed in a server backend, which implies usage 24 hours a day, potentially for several years. Even under the assumption that most accesses will be read-only, the amount of data stored in the database will inevitably increase over time, because every modification and even delete operation will result in an increase in data volume as new versions need to be managed. Even though our current implementation, which stores all data in a single B⁺ tree, scales well to 100.000 entries and beyond, it will inevitably reach its limits when being operated for several years. In order to support this use case, the following criteria must be met:

- **R1: Support for an extended number of versions**

As many versions will accumulate over years, the scalability limits of a single B-Tree structure will eventually be exceeded, causing greatly increased query times at best and system crashes at worst. The system must not be constrained by such limitations and offer support for a virtually unlimited number of versions.

- **R2: Support for efficient file-based backup**

In server backend scenarios, the contents of a database are often backed up by automated tools at regular intervals. In order to reduce the load of such tools, the database must be segmented into files such that most files remain the same when new data is being added, allowing effective detection of unchanged files via checksums.

- **R3: Support for efficient access to old versions**

Queries that request older versions of data should not be inherently slower than queries operating on recent versions. In particular, a linear correlation between the age of a requested version and resulting query performance must be avoided.

Together, those requirements describe the environment in which our database will need to operate. In the next section, we will outline our solution and how it meets those requirements.

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The primary requirement, as outlined in Section III, is the ability to support a virtually unlimited number of versions [R1]. Also, we must not store all data in a single file, and old files should ideally remain untouched when inserting new data [R2]. For these reasons, we must not constrain our solution to a single B-Tree. The fact that past revisions are immutable in our approach coincides with requirement [R2], so we decided to split the data along the time axis, resulting in a series of B-Trees. Each tree is contained in one file, which we refer to as a *chunk file*. An accompanying *meta file* specifies the time range which is covered by the chunk file. The usual policy of ChronoDB is to maximize sharing of unchanged data as much as possible. Here, we deliberately introduce data duplication in order to ensure that the initial version in each chunk is complete. This allows us to answer *get* queries within the boundaries of a single chunk, without having to navigate to the previous one. As each access to another chunk has CPU and

Fig. 2. The temporal rollover process by example

I/O overhead, we cannot afford to access more than one chunk to answer a basic query. Without duplication, accessing a key that has not changed for a long time could potentially lead to a linear search through the chunk chain, violating requirement [R3].

The algorithm for the “rollover” procedure outlined in Figure 2 works as follows.

Algorithm 1: Temporal Rollover

Data: The data chunk containing the “head” revision

Result: An archive chunk and a new “head” chunk

- 1 $time \leftarrow \text{getLastTimestamp}(\text{headChunk});$
 - 2 $head \leftarrow \text{getHeadRevisionFromChunk}(\text{headChunk});$
 - 3 $\text{setValidTo}(\text{headChunk}, \text{time});$
 - 4 $\text{newHeadChunk} \leftarrow \text{createEmptyChunk}(\text{time} + 1);$
 - 5 $\text{insertEntriesIntoChunk}(\text{head}, \text{newHeadChunk});$
 - 6 $\text{updateTimeRangeLookup}();$
-

In Line 1 of Algorithm 1, we fetch the latest timestamp where a commit has occurred in our current head revision chunk. Next, we calculate the full head version of the data in Line 2. With the preparation steps complete, we set the end of the validity time range to the last commit timestamp in Line 3. This only affects the metadata, not the chunk itself. We now create a new, empty chunk in Line 4, and set the start of its validity range to the split timestamp plus one (as chunk validity ranges must not overlap). The upper bound of the new validity range is infinity. In Line 5 we copy the head version of the data into the new chunk. Finally, we update our internal lookup table in Line 6. This entire procedure only modifies the last chunk and does not touch older chunks, as indicated by the grayed-out boxes in Figure 2.

The lookup table that is being updated in Algorithm 1 is a basic tree map which is created at startup by reading the metadata files. For each encountered chunk, it contains an entry that maps its validity period to its chunk file. The periods are sorted in ascending order by their lower bounds, which is sufficient because overlaps in the validity ranges are not permitted. For example, after the rollover depicted in Figure 2, the time range lookup would contain the entries shown in Table II.

TABLE II
TIME RANGE LOOKUP

Time Range	Chunk Number
[0...300]	0
[301...1000]	1
[1001...∞]	2

We employ a tree map specifically in our implementation for Table II, because the purpose of this lookup is to quickly identify the correct chunk to address for an incoming request. Incoming requests have a timestamp attached, and this timestamp may occur exactly at a split, or anywhere between split timestamps. As this process is triggered very often in practice and the time range lookup map may grow quite large over time, we are considering to implement a cache based on the least-recently-used principle that contains the concrete resolved timestamp-to-chunk mappings in order to cover the common case where one particular timestamp is requested more than once in quick succession.

With this algorithm, we can support all three of our previously identified requirements (see Section III). We achieve support for a virtually unlimited number of versions [R1] because new chunks always only contain the head revision of the previous ones, and we are always free to roll over once more should the history within the chunk become too large. We furthermore do not perform writes on old chunk files anymore, because our history is immutable [R2]. Regardless, thanks to our time range lookup, we have close to $O(\log n)$ access complexity to any chunk [R3], where n is the number of chunks, with the additional possibility of caching frequently used timestamp-to-chunk mappings.

This algorithm is a trade-off between disk space and scalability. We introduce data duplication on disk in order to provide support for large histories. The key question that remains is *when* this process happens. We need a metric that indicates the amount of data in the current chunk that belongs to the history (as opposed to the head revision) and thus can be archived if necessary by performing a rollover. We introduce the *Head-History-Ratio* (HHR) as the primary metric for this task, which we defined as follows:

$$HHR(e, h) = \begin{cases} e, & \text{if } e = h \\ \frac{h}{e-h}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

...where e is the total number of entries in the chunk, and h is the size of the subset of entries that belong to the head revision (excluding entries that represent deletions). By dividing the number of entries in the head revision by the number of entries that belong to the history, we get a proportional notion of how much history is contained in the chunk that works for datasets of any size. It expresses how many entries we will “archive” when a rollover is executed. When new commits add new elements to the head revision, this value increases. When a commit updates existing elements in the head revision or deletes them, this value decreases. We can employ a threshold as a lower bound on this value

to determine when a rollover is necessary. For example, we may choose to perform a rollover when a chunk has an HHR value of 0.2 or less. This threshold will work independently of the absolute size of the head revision. The only case where the HHR threshold is never reached is when exclusively new (i.e. never seen before) keys are added, steadily increasing the size of the head revision. However, in this case we would not gain anything by performing a rollover, as we would have to duplicate all of those entries into the new chunk to produce a complete initial version, therefore the HHR metric is properly capturing this case by never reaching the threshold, thus never indicating the need for a rollover.

V. DISCUSSION & RELATED WORK

Even though data versioning has been recognized as an important problem in academic literature for many years, the sustainability of the versioning process itself is rarely discussed in related work. For example, in the SQL-based *ImmortalDB* system [4], every time an entry overrides another one, a pointer is created from the current to the previous version, forming a history chain. The resulting system offers good performance on the head revision and recent versions, but the access times increase linearly as the request timestamp is moved further back in time, because the history chains need to be traversed linearly.

Felber et al. propose a similar solution [3] for key-value stores. Here, each key refers to a list of value versions. Again, the search for older entries is linear. This approach furthermore suffers from the loss of coherence information - the second entry in the list for key a may have existed at the same time as the tenth entry for key b , but this information is lost.

The solution proposed by Ramaswamy [2] does not suffer from any of these drawbacks and is conceptually much closer to our solution. Ramaswamy proposes to have validity intervals for key-value pairs and perform the search over these intervals. In the paper, the drawback of having to update the upper bounds of the validity ranges is clearly explained, which is the main difference to our versioning approach. However, Ramaswamy does not propose a concrete implementation, and therefore does not touch upon the issue of sustainability.

Our solution offers an access time to any version of any key in $O(\log c + \log e)$ accesses, where c is the number of chunks and e is the number of entries in the target chunk. If we assume a cache with $O(1)$ access time for the most frequently used request timestamps, the complexity is reduced to $O(\log e)$. We would like to emphasize that e is the number of entries in a single chunk, and therefore only represents a fraction of the overall history. Even without such a cache, with a reasonable choice for the HHR threshold, the number of chunks will always be significantly smaller than the total number of entries, and the resulting time range lookup table is small enough to be held in-memory, which further decreases the access times. In order to achieve these advantages, our approach relies on data duplication on disk, which increases the footprint of the database. In our case this duplication does not introduce synchronization issues, because only existing versions are duplicated, which are immutable in our system.

The challenging part is the implementation itself, because the rollover process has to be implemented in a way that is safe against crashes and immediate program termination. For example, when a rollover is taking place and the program is terminated by an external signal, then at restart the database needs to be able to infer the correct steps for reaching a consistent state again. This recovery process in turn needs to be safe against crashes and needs to be repeatable an arbitrary number of times without ever leading to a non-recoverable state.

VI. OUTLOOK & FUTURE WORK

Using the versioning concepts presented in this paper, we are implementing a versioned graph database compatible with the Apache TinkerPop API³ which will soon be officially announced. Our final goal is to make use of this versioned graph database in order to implement a modern, efficient and feature-rich repository for EMF⁴ models.

VII. SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented our approach for a sustainable data versioning process. Based on our previous work [6] we employed a key-value format in order to keep the complexity of the versioning problem to a minimum. We presented a summary of our existing technology, and provided an overview of our efforts to transition the prototype into a software tool that can run for several years in a server backend and deal with the resulting large amounts of data. The method is based upon a *rollover* process, which takes the current (immutable) head revision and copies it into a new, empty data structure, where it will continue to evolve as new changes are applied. We also introduced a metric called *Head-History-Ratio* (HHR) which provides an estimate when a rollover should be executed based on the contents of the database. Finally, we compared our approach to existing related work and provided a discussion on the individual advantages, disadvantages and challenges.

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³<https://tinkerpop.apache.org/>

⁴<https://www.eclipse.org/modeling/emf/>